

Choosing Optimal Path Routing for Emergency Vehicles on Yangon Road Network

Ei Swe Han*

Abstract

Transportation of a patient to emergency hospital seems quite simple but in actuality, it is quite difficult and it became more difficult in heavy traffic condition. Now roads are so congested especially in cities, that it is difficult for the emergency vehicles to travel and reach the hospital from the accident point. Road network information is always changing such as closing some road for maintenance, during rush hour, around a sport race, car accident and traffic congestions when emergency vehicle travelling on the road network. Emergency vehicle has to choose the new optimal path when the current path is disturbance occur. This Emergency Vehicle Management System (EVMS) provides to solve both static and dynamic routing problems and to find the optimal path for emergency vehicle when an accident occurs on Yangon City road network.

Key words: road network, emergency vehicle

Introduction

In today's world, emergency services are necessary when accident occurs on the road network and need to save human lives. Transportation of a patient to a hospital seems quite simple but in actuality, it is quite difficult and it becomes more difficult during peak hours. Once the emergency vehicle gets stuck in traffic, it takes more time to reach the hospital. Most of the emergency vehicles take the patient to the hospital as less as possible, even though they are unable to reach the hospital because of huge traffic at junctions.

This proposed system, the optimal path is considered as finding a path between two specific points in both static and dynamic road network which needs minimum distance to traverse. When road conditions are changed, the algorithm finds the new path which is the optimal path because it is shorter than the other. Optimal

path routing is often used for routing emergency vehicles such as ambulance, fire engine and police car. In some cases the optimal path has to be determined in a few seconds in order to ensure the safety of a patient. Moreover, when large real road networks are involved in an application, the determination of shortest paths on a large network can be computationally very intensive. Because many applications involve real road networks, computation of a shortest path (optimal path) requires an answer in real time.

Computing optimal routes in road networks is one of the showpieces of real world applications of algorithm. A key problem in road network and transportation analysis is the computation of shortest paths between different locations on a real road network. A road network can easily be represented as a graph. Dijkstra's algorithm is the classic solution from graph theory. Several shortest path algorithms have been suggested by the researchers and Dijkstra's shortest path algorithm is the most appropriate one, which can be extended with a variety of modifications. Taking the real road networks into consideration, Dijkstra's algorithms have to be modified.

* Dr, Lecturer, Department of Computer Science, Dagon University

Choosing Optimal Path Routing for Emergency Vehicle on Yangon Road Network

Ei Swe Han*

Abstract

Transportation of a patient to emergency hospital seems quite simple but in actuality, it is difficult and it became more difficult in heavy traffic condition. Now roads are so congested especially in cities, that it is difficult for the emergency vehicles to travel and reach the hospital from the accident point. Road network information is always changing such as closed road for maintenance, during rush hour, around a sport race, car accident and traffic congestion when emergency vehicle travelling on the road network. Emergency vehicle has to choose a new optimal path when the current path is disturbed. This Emergency Vehicle Management System (EVMS) provides to solve both static and dynamic routing problems to find the optimal path for emergency vehicle when an accident occurs on Yangon City road network.

Key words: road network, emergency vehicle

Introduction

In today's world, emergency services are necessary when an accident occurs on a road network and need to save human lives. Transportation of a patient to a hospital is simple but in actuality, it is quite difficult and it becomes more difficult during heavy traffic. Once the emergency vehicle gets stuck in traffic, it takes more time to reach the hospital. The goal of the emergency vehicles is to take the patient to the hospital as less as possible, even if they are unable to reach the hospital because of huge traffic at junctions.

This proposed system, the optimal path is considered as finding a path between specific points in both static and dynamic road network which needs minimum time to traverse. When road conditions are changed, the algorithm finds the new path as the optimal path because it is shorter than the other. Optimal

path routing is often used for routing emergency vehicles such as ambulance, fire truck, and police car. In some cases the optimal path has to be determined in a few seconds to ensure the safety of a patient. Moreover, when large real road networks are used in an application, the determination of shortest paths on a large network can be computationally intensive. Because many applications involve real road networks, computation of an optimal path (optimal path) requires an answer in real time.

Computing optimal routes in road networks is one of the showpieces of graph theory applications of algorithm. A key problem in road network and transportation is the computation of shortest paths between different locations on a real road network. A road network can easily be represented as a graph. Dijkstra's algorithm is the classic algorithm in graph theory. Several shortest path algorithms have been suggested by the researchers. Dijkstra's shortest path algorithm is the most appropriate one, which can be ex-

Objectives

Emergency Vehicle Management System (EVMS) is presented to solve both static and dynamic routing problems and to find the optimal path for emergency vehicle when an accident occurs on Yangon City road network. The main objective of this study is EVMS to help the emergency vehicle travel to the nearest hospital or desired hospital as fast as possible without getting delay due to the congestion on road network for saving the injured person. Furthermore, this research intends to provide the optimal path routing for emergency vehicle such as ambulances, police cars, even taxi or any emergency cars that can take the injured person to the hospital rapidly when accident occurred in Yangon City.

Creating Road Map and Road Network

The spatial data of the GIS are used for creating road network. The road and traffic data are the essential information of a city's transportation road network. Road network is necessary for emergency vehicles to travel. GIS information based road network is used only background image for the system. GIS information is supported by Google Map application. Google Maps servers deliver, upon processing the request from the client, calculate the parts of the world map (tiles) at the specific zoom level. Tiles are a part of the simple coordinate system based on the latitude and longitude pair of the point on the world map and rendered at a certain zoom level.

After sending the request Google Maps servers can offer the required map shown in the following figure 1. Save these downloaded tiles to use later (Offline). If tile row, tile column and zoom level of require map have not downloaded into the local file, request and download from the Google Maps server and OSM to save in the local file. If require map tiles have been saved in the local file it can reuse this downloaded tiles for next time no need to request again or in offline. The downloaded tiles are saved from the local file to database as tile row, tile column and zoom level.

Figure 1 Google Maps Server Offers the Required Map

Data Source of Google Maps

To acquire a road image of specific city around the Earth, Google Maps application was used. Google Maps freely support raster data format of road network only. Raster data is characterized by pixel values. Satellite imagery uses raster data to record different wavelengths of light. A raster file is a giant table, where each pixel is assigned a specific value from 0 to 255. Figure 2 represents a captured road map of Yangon City from Google Map as an example.

Objectives

Emergency Vehicle Management System (EVMS) is presented to solve the dynamic routing problems and to find the optimal path for emergency vehicles when an accident occurs on Yangon City road network. The main objective of this study is to help the emergency vehicle travel to the nearest hospital or desired hospital as fast as possible without getting delay due to the congestion on road network for saving the lives. Furthermore, this research intends to provide the optimal path routing for emergency vehicles such as ambulances, police cars, even taxi or any emergency cars that can take a person to the hospital rapidly when an accident occurred in Yangon City.

Creating Road Map and Road Network

The spatial data of the GIS are used for creating road network. The road data are the essential information of a city's transportation road network. Road network data are used for emergency vehicles to travel. GIS information based road network is used on a map image for the system. GIS information is supported by Google Map application. Google Map servers deliver, upon processing the request from the client, calculate the parts of the map (tiles) at the specific zoom level. Tiles are a part of the simple coordinate system where the latitude and longitude pair of the point on the world map are rendered at a specific zoom level.

After sending the request Google Maps servers can offer the required map tiles following figure 1. Save these downloaded tiles to use later (Offline). If tile rows and zoom level of required map have not been downloaded into the local file, request tiles from the Google Maps server and OSM to save in the local file. If required map tiles are saved in the local file, it can reuse these downloaded tiles for next time, no need to request tiles or in offline. The downloaded tiles are saved from the local file to database as a column and zoom level.

Figure 1 Google Maps Server Offers the Required Map

Figure 2 Road Map of Yangon City

Data Source of OpenStreetMap (OSM)

Geographical information of the road network is obtained from OpenStreetMap (OSM). OSM is freely supported for vector data format. Vector data is the spatial data represented as points, lines and polygons. This system of demo features is based on the intersection between arcs and nodes. A point is a single node, a line is two nodes with an arc between them and a polygon is a closed group of three or more arcs [3].

Besides the road network, there are also rivers, buildings and even trees present. All information of nodes and ways (the OSM term for all different kinds of roads) is stripped from the downloaded data. This data is saved to the database which is used it to construct the road network. The length of arcs connecting two nodes is calculated using the geographic coordinates (latitude, longitude) of the nodes. OSM data is clear and exact for calculating and processing shortest path. Therefore, in this system the OSM layer is partly covered onto the Google road map. Figure 3 shows that OSM layer is partly covered onto Yangon road map.

Figure 3 Yangon Road Map of OSM

Addition of Resources on the Road Network

The road network serves as an underlying reference system for all resources that are part of an Emergency Vehicle Management System (EVMS). The system is modeled by the following resources on the static road network.

Hospitals

Hospitals provide medical care to injured and sick people. To save a patient, the only way is to take the nearest hospital. The proposed system is supported of the optimal path routing for emergency vehicle to the nearest hospital or desired hospital. In this system,

Figure 2 Road Map of Yangon City

Data Source of OpenStreetMap (OSM)

Geographical information of the road network is obtained from OpenStreetMap (OSM). OSM is freely supported for vector data format. Vector data is the spatial data in the form of points, lines and polygons. This system of demo features is based on the intersection of arcs and nodes. A point is a single node, a line is two nodes with an arc between them, and a polygon is a closed group of three or more arcs [3].

Besides the road network, there are also rivers, buildings and even tree information of nodes and ways (the OSM term for all different kinds of roads) is included in the downloaded data. This data is saved to the database which is used to construct the road network. The length of arcs connecting two nodes is calculated using the coordinates (latitude, longitude) of the nodes. OSM data is clear and exact for computing shortest path. Therefore, in this system the OSM layer is partly covered onto Google road map. Figure 3 shows the OSM layer is partly covered onto Yangon road map.

Figure 3 Yangon Road Map of OSM

Addition of Resources on the Road Network

The road network serves as an underlying reference system for all resources in the part of an Emergency Vehicle Management System (EVMS). The system is m

locations of some hospitals are placed on the map of Yangon City. Figure 4 shows the hospitals are placed on the Yangon road map.

Figure 4 Hospitals on the Yangon Road Map

Database for System

Geographic information of roads and junctions are needed for creating road network. This information is available by Google Maps and OSM that is saved in the SQLite database as their location of latitude and longitude coordinate with their names. All hospitals and junctions are saved into the database.

Google’s Road Map of Yangon

Map of Yangon city are requested from the Google Map server and download the return file. Then the available map is saved to the database like SQLite database files with table name “tiles” include “zoom_level”, “tile_column” and “tile_row” as the following table 1.

Table 1 SQLite database files of Google Road Map

sr. no.	zoom_level	tile_column	tile_row
1	7	68	63
2	7	68	65
3	7	97	58
4	5	16	16

Names and Locations of Hospitals

Some Hospitals are placed on the road network. New hospital names can add and save to the SQLite database as table name “Department” with hospital’s name and latitude and longitude of its location. Table 2 shows SQLite database file of hospital’s location.

locations of some hospitals are placed on the map of Yangon City. Figure hospitals are placed on the Yangon road map.

Figure 4 Hospitals on the Yangon Road Map

Database for System

Geographic information of roads and junctions are needed for creating road network. This information is available by Google Maps and OSM that is saved in the SQLite database with their location of latitude and longitude coordinate with their names. All hospitals are saved into the database.

Google’s Road Map of Yangon

Map of Yangon city are requested from the Google Map server and downloaded as a return file. Then the available map is saved to the database like SQLite database with table name “tiles” include “zoom_level”, “tile_column” and “tile_row” as the following.

Table 1 SQLite database files of Google Road Map

sr. no.	zoom_level	tile_column	tile_row
1	7	68	63
2	7	68	65
3	7	97	58
4	5	16	16

Table 2 Locations of Hospitals in the SQLite Database

sr. no.	name	type	latitude	longitude
1	Yangon General Hospital	1	16.778616	96.15067
2	Bahosi Hospital	1	16.779715	96.140018
3	Military Hospital No 2	1	16.78787	96.148181
4	Paragu Hospital	1	16.776694	96.169295
5	Academy Hospital	1	16.790526	96.127995
6	SSC Hospital	1	16.810873	96.165503

Dijkstra’s Shortest Path Algorithm for Network Analysis

Network Analysis for optimal path routing is based on the well-known Dijkstra's shortest path algorithm. Dijkstra's algorithm, conceived by computer scientist Edsger Dijkstra in 1956 and published in 1959, is a graph search algorithm that solves the single-source shortest path problem for a graph with non-negative edge path costs, producing a shortest path tree [2].

The classical Dijkstra's algorithm solves a shortest path problem directed and nonnegative weighted graph. Bidirectional dynamic shortest path algorithm is modified based on the original Dijkstra’s algorithm for better performance of finding shortest path. Bidirectional search is a graph search algorithm that finds a shortest path from an initial vertex to a goal vertex in directed graph. It runs two simultaneous searches: one forward from the initial state and one backward from the goal, stop it when the two meet in the middle. To use it within the context of real-world transportation data, this algorithm is modified to respect real time information such as blocked road segment congestion while finding shortest or optimal path.

Figure 5 Shortest Path Tree of Dijkstra's Algorithm

Table 2 Locations of Hospitals in the SQLite Database

sr. no.	name	type	latitude	longitude
1	Yangon General Hospital	1	16.778616	96.15067
2	Bahosi Hospital	1	16.779715	96.140018
3	Military Hospital No 2	1	16.78787	96.148181
4	Paragu Hospital	1	16.776694	96.169295
5	Academy Hospital	1	16.790526	96.127995
6	SSC Hospital	1	16.810873	96.165503

Dijkstra's Shortest Path Algorithm for Network Analysis

Network Analysis for optimal path routing is based on the well-known shortest path algorithm. Dijkstra's algorithm, conceived by computer scientist E in 1956 and published in 1959, is a graph search algorithm that solves the shortest path problem for a graph with non-negative edge path costs, producing a tree [2].

The classical Dijkstra's algorithm solves a shortest path problem on a nonnegative weighted graph. Bidirectional dynamic shortest path algorithm is an extension on the original Dijkstra's algorithm for better performance of finding a shortest path. Bidirectional search is a graph search algorithm that finds a shortest path from an initial vertex to a goal vertex in directed graph. It runs two simultaneous searches from the initial state and one backward from the goal, stop it when the two meet. To use it within the context of real-world transportation data, this algorithm is used to find an optimal path in respect to real time information such as blocked road segment congestion while finding an optimal path.

Figure 6 Search Space of Dijkstra's Algorithm

Figure 7 Search Space of Bidirectional Dijkstra's Algorithm

Choosing Optimal Path on Road Network

Optimal Path Routing on Static Road Network

In static road network, the road network condition is a normal that means it has no blocked junctions and no blocked road segments. An accident location is identified on the road network. Figure 8 shows the accident name, accident type, location of accident point as latitude and longitude while the accident point is placed on the road network.

Figure 8 Identified Accident Locations

After the accident point is placed on the road network, the system calculates and finds the optimal path by using bidirectional dynamic Dijkstra's shortest path algorithm. Figure 9 describes the optimal path routing from the accident point to the nearest hospital and other hospitals.

Figure 6 Search Space of Dijkstra's Algorithm

Figure 7 Search Space of Bidirectional Dijkstra's Algorithm

Choosing Optimal Path on Road Network

Optimal Path Routing on Static Road Network

In static road network, the road network condition is a normal that means no blocked junctions and no blocked road segments. An accident location is identified on the road network. Figure 8 shows the accident name, accident type, location of accident point, latitude, and longitude while the accident point is placed on the road network.

Conditions

Add Condition Remove Condition

Accident Site

Type Car accident

Latitude 16.82048

Longitude 95.17637

Emergency Department

Name

Latitude

Longitude

Name	Type	Latitude	Longitude
Yango	Hospital	16.773	95.151
Bahosi	Hospital	16.779	95.140
Military	Hospital	16.787	95.140
P. Pranga	Hospital	16.775	95.1603
Acade	Hospital	16.790	95.128
SSC A	Hospital	16.810	95.166
Asia R	Hospital	16.799	95.131
East Y	Hospital	16.771	95.174
Yanton	Hospital	16.838	95.158
Pun H	Hospital	16.840	95.089
Victoria	Hospital	16.877	95.1301
Carhop	Hospital	16.816	95.122
im	Hospital	16.782	95.173

Optimal Path:

Figure 9 Optimal Paths from the Accident Point to the Nearest Hospital and other Hospitals

Identified the Desired Hospital

If one wants to go to desired hospital, the system allows to choose the desired hospital and shows the optimal path between accident point and this hospital. In the following figure 10, the system finds and shows the optimal path from the accident point to selected hospital. For example, if desire to go Orthopedic Hospital, select Orthopedic Hospital and the system shows the optimal path from the accident point to Orthopedic Hospital.

Figure 10 Optimal Path from the Accident Point to the Desired Hospital

Optimal Path Routing on Dynamic Road Network

Finding the shortest path for dynamic road network is as different as the static road network. The original path is changed when the road is congested during emergency vehicle travel to destination. So the new optimal path will have to be considered. For solving this dynamic problem, the algorithm changed the weight of the arcs and recalculates the shortest path for the new optimal path.

Addition of Real Time Block Road Segment on the Selected Path

If the road is congested on the selected path, the system allows by adding real time block road segment to selected path. Algorithm finds the other optimal path avoiding that congested road and then shows the new optimal path. In figure 11 shows real time blocked on the selected path and show the new optimal path.

Figure 9 Optimal Paths from the Accident Point to the Nearest Hospital and other Hospitals

Identified the Desired Hospital

If one wants to go to desired hospital, the system allows to choose the desired hospital and shows the optimal path between accident point and this hospital. In the following figure 10, the system finds and shows the optimal path from the accident point to selected hospital. For example, if desire to go Orthopedic Hospital, select Orthopedic Hospital and the system shows the optimal path from the accident point to Orthopedic Hospital.

Figure 10 Optimal Path from the Accident Point to the Desired Hospital

Optimal Path Routing on Dynamic Road Network

Finding the shortest path for dynamic road network is as different as static network. The original path is changed when the road is congested during emergency travel to destination. So the new optimal path will have to be considered. For dynamic problem, the algorithm changed the weight of the arcs and recalculate the path for the new optimal path.

Figure 11 New Optimal Path When Adding Block on the Selected Path

Conclusion

The proposed system is finding the optimal path routing for emergency vehicle by analyzing road network of Yangon City. In Yangon City, the vehicles are increasing daily, at the same time the congestions are caused on road networks. During taking a patient to the hospital, these problems are faced by the emergency vehicles. Emergency Vehicle Management System (EVMS) is designed to the analysis of the road network of Yangon city by using Dijkstra's dynamic shortest path algorithm effectively.

EVMS provides the optimal path routing to the nearest hospital, desired hospital and other hospitals from the accident point. When road condition has changed with time more frequently, the system can find many optimal paths routing between the accident point and destination hospital. Therefore, EVMS is an efficient and interactive system for network analysis of optimal path routing on both static and dynamic road network.

As for a future work, EVMS will consider the multi parameters such as time taken to travel from the source to destination, real time road condition of blocked or unblocked junction, etc.

Acknowledgements

First of all I would like to acknowledge Dr Win Naing, Rector of Dagon University, for his all valuable advice and encouragement on this paper. I am also thankful to Dr Yi Mon Win (Associate Professor), Head of Department of Computer Studies, Dagon University for her help in this paper.

References

- Darkomen, "GoogleMaps-Control for NET",
<http://www.codeproject.com/Articles/463434/GoogleMapsNet-GoogleMaps-Control-for-NET> , version 1.0, September 2012.
- Melissa Yan, "Dijkstra's Algorithm",
<http://www.math.mit.edu/presentations/1-Melissa.pdf>, Feb 29, 2014.
- OpenStreetMap(OSM)
<http://www.en.wikipedia.org/wiki/OpenStreetMap>.

Figure 11 New Optimal Path When Adding Block on the Selected Pa

Conclusion

The proposed system is finding the optimal path routing for emergency analyzing road network of Yangon City. In Yangon City, the vehicles are increas the same time the congestions are caused on road networks. During taking a hospital, these problems are faced by the emergency vehicles. Emergency Management System (EVMS) is designed to the analysis of the road network o by using Dijkstra’s dynamic shortest path algorithm effectively.

EVMS provides the optimal path routing to the nearest hospital, desired other hospitals from the accident point. When road condition has changed wi frequently, the system can find many optimal paths routing between the accid destination hospital. Therefore, EVMS is an efficient and interactive system analysis of optimal path routing on both static and dynamic road network.

As for a future work, EVMS will consider the multi parameters such as travel from the source to destination, real time road condition of blocked junction, etc.

Acknowledgements

First of all I would like to acknowledge Dr Win Naing, Rector of Dagon University, for advice and encouragement on this paper. I am also thankful to Dr Yi Mon Win (Associate Pro Department of Computer Studies, Dagon University for her help in this paper.

References

Darkomen, “ GoogleMaps-Control for NET”,

1. “ GoogleMaps-Control for NET”,